

CHANGE IN AN ORGANISATION CREATES AN IMPACT: INSIGHTS FROM INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

Change is difficult for organisations to prevent since new concepts spur development. Their efforts will help them and their members advance. Change is essential to any firm because changes are made via adjusting. This study's aim is to discover how employees perceive a change in an organisation. Any business, especially top management, finds it challenging to plan for and manage behaviour changes that affect the level of stress experienced by the organisation and its staff. If not, the company would logically exceed its active limit and stop being effective at identifying customers' demands. In order to assess how employees feel about change brought about in an organisation, a survey was undertaken among the staff of a private IT company.

Keywords: Change, perception, employee performance, organization change, implementation, management.

1. Introduction:

1.1. Perception:

Perception is a "multipart course by which people choose, systematise, and understand sensory inspiration into an important and logical representation of the universe," according to Wikipedia (Berelson and Steiner, 1964: 88). Perception is concerned with "receiving, selecting, acquiring, transforming, and organising the sequence finished by our mind" in a comparable layer (Barber and Legge, 1976). Perceptual outcomes have been linked to Bartlett's (1932) important function of knowledge's optimistic behavior. This is different in that it describes how an individual's normal view of the world's influences and qualities adjusts in a series of processes. Anderson and Paine (1975) proposed that an organization's perception of the need for change is effected by its perception of environmental unpredictability.

1. Perception is a subtle aspect that is intertwined with other factors such as activities and mental strength. Still, it will be interesting to see how these raises differ; the majority, if not all, appear to contribute to regular assets.

2. Human perceptions influence how people perceive their surroundings and make decisions. Understanding how people perceive the world can help us better understand how people make decisions and act in certain ways.

1.2. Organisation change:

Organizational change happens when a business moves from its present situation to a selected opportunity. The act of anticipating and implementing change in an organisation in a way that reduces costs and employee resentment while maximising the benefits of the change effort is known as managing organisational change. An energetic viewpoint claims that organisational change happens as a result of a dynamic environment or in reaction to a pressing issue at hand. Teams made up of individuals transition or change as a result of change. Aiming to assist stakeholders in embracing and sustaining change in both their professional and personal lives, it is a business practise.

1.2.1. Organisational change need and importance:

Business executives would keep giving secretaries instructions for communication, tweak the phrasing, and then send it back for further work if nothing changed, which would take time away from other tasks. The outcome of new technology adoption, Forbes claims that most firms go through change. Although the shift may initially be disruptive, it usually has a long-term positive impact on productivity and service performance.

Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; David, Ahmed, Ganeshkumar & Sankar, 2020; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018). Businesspeople no longer use rotary phones to make calls, get a busy signal, and keep trying until they connect. To find out about other people who could be useful resources, businesspeople no longer need to create time-consuming personal contacts. They can now use search engines and social media websites to look for expertise online. The fast evolving communication technology of today reflects developments that make it possible for organisations to learn more and more quickly than ever. Examining how employees perceive change is the main objective.

2. Review of literature:

Organizational change involves changing employee attitudes and behaviours from the known to the unknown in order to assess the capacities of managers, workers, and the workplace. Some researches concentrated on modifications that might be detrimental to staff morale. 2001 (Weber & Weber). Therefore, encouraging positive employee attitudes enhances staff readiness, an essential element for a successful organisational transformation (Rafferty & Simon, 2006; Bareil et al., 2007).

Commitment, according to Mowday et al. (1982), attitude reflects the type and quality of the relationship between an individual and also an organisation. To achieve these goals, an individual must identify with a specific organisation and its goals in order to maintain membership. The most critical predictor of organisational change attitudes and perceptions.

In other words, employees who have a high level of organisational commitment are more likely to put up extra effort in a change project and afterwards are more likely to form favourable

views toward organisational change. Directly and indirectly, job satisfaction with particular job components influences many aspects of organizational change attitudes. (Yousef, 2000).

According to Karyn E. Trader-Leigh (2001), Change and organizational change require rigorous effort. Change does not succeed because the environment resists it and does not recognize the strength of individual systems. Individual resistance to change is influenced by people's personal and emotional experiences as well as the prevalence of norms, traditions, compatibility, and supportive factors. Professional pressure, according to Maria Vakalo (2005), is associated with negative attitudes toward change. Tension caused by onerous tasks with a high burden and unequal pay can lead to a negative attitude toward organisational change and, as a result, keep the organisation in the process.

Employee attitude is proactively determined by the surroundings, as well as their individual objectives and morals, according to Lan Coa (2013). Hechanava (2003) contends that for change to be beneficial, employees must feel appropriately informed and trained, particularly during change-supportive comments, as this will minimise anxiety and uncertainty and, thus, change resistance.

Ming-Chu Yu (2009) looked at how employees perceive organisational change and how religion and stress management strategies influence their perspectives. In 450 surveyable questionnaires, employees from four Taiwanese government departments facing transition were polled. The Department of Defense, Coast Guard, National Police Agency and Fire and Disaster Management Agency conducted all investigations. The findings showed that organisational change significantly lowers employees' attachment to and belief in their jobs. Stress management techniques and an understanding of organisational change can be used to influence employees' organisational awareness and work attachment in a beneficial way. Therefore, stress management training can be implemented in a business going through a leadership transition to offer stress-relieving alternatives as well as to enhance organisational recognition and job satisfaction among employees.

Employee perceptions of the advantage in technique evaluation accuracy and equality of assistance helped predict involvement (Ogilvie, 1986). Employee attitudes are closely linked to beliefs about an organization's commitment to employee benefits such as training and development, and employee engagement is closely linked to HR policies. An organization's efforts to change might be aided or hampered by employee perceptions of leadership's change readiness (Ebay et al.2000).

Theoretical evidence suggests that organisational change produces unique employee attitudes, behaviours, and perceptions that give the company confidence and are always associated with the development and expansion of the organisation. (Gaertner and Nollen, 1989, 3)

3. Methodology:

A descriptive research design is employed, and primary data is gathered using a standardised questionnaire. Latham and Kinne's work inspired the development of an organisational change-based instrument (1973, 1974). A convenience sampling method was used to select employees

from a private company. The study's sample size is 30 employees from IT firms. Frequency and mean analysis are used to analyse the collected data.

4. Data analysis and interpretation:

A simple frequency test was performed to understand the demographic distribution of the respondents.

4.1. Demographic characteristics of the employees

Table.1: Demographic characteristics of the employees

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	12	40.0
Female	18	60.0
Total	30	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percent
< 23 years	10	33.3
23-28 years	12	40.0
>28 years	8	26.7
Total	30	100.0
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
UG	15	50.0
PG	14	46.7

It is inferred from the above table, 18 (60 %) of the 30 respondents are female, while 12 (40%) are male. The sample includes people of all ages. The majority of respondents (40%) are between the ages of 23 and 28. The majority of respondents are UG graduates (50 %). As a result, It is clear that the survey yielded responses from a wide variety of respondents that appropriately reflected the diversity of the workforce across the selected IT companies.

4.2. Perception of Employees towards Organizational Change:

Based on the 13 items, following factor was identified such as Implementation of change, Involvement of management during change, Employee relation to change, consequences of change, Enhancement by change towards organizational change and its mean analysis was displayed in table no.2.

Table 2: Perception of employees during organizational change

S. No	Perception Of Employees During Organisational Change	Mean	Rank
	Implementation of change:		
1	Change is made to improve organisation (improvement)	2.50	6
2	Employees co-operate during change (co-operation)	2.63	2
3	Employees are sufficiently informed about change (sufficiency)	2.40	10
	Involvement of management during change:		
1	Consultation to departments about change (consultation)	2.42	9
2	Corporate management's involvement during change (corporate's involvement)	2.51	5
	Employee's relation to change:		
1	Enhancement of one's position during organisation change (enhancement)	2.53	3
2	Employees involvement during change (employees' involvement)	2.52	4
3	Good communication between project leaders and employees (communication)	2.43	8
	Consequences of change:		
1	Large scale changes influence department goals (goals)	2.90	1
2	Some changes are made time to time in the organisation (time to time)	2.37	11
3	Some resistance to change among employees (resistance)	2.30	12
	Enhancement by change:		
1	Change in organisation affects individual performance (individual performance)	1.83	8
2	Discussion of changes with concerned employees (discussion)	2.44	7

Implementation of change:

Table 2 displays the mean score and rank. It reveals that the variable "Cooperation" has the highest average score of 2.63, followed by Improvement (2.50) and Sufficiency (2.40). All of the mean scores range from 2 to 3. It concludes that respondents agree on all of the factors mentioned.

Involvement of management during change:

It demonstrates that the variable "Corporate involvement" has the average mean score of 2.50, followed by Consultation (2.43). The average scores range from 2 to 3. It concludes that respondents agree on all of the factors mentioned.

Employees' relation to change:

It shows that the variable "Enhancement" has the highest average score of 2.53, followed by Employees' involvement (2.52) and Communication (2.43). The average scores range from 2 to 3. It concludes that respondents agree on all of the factors mentioned.

Consequences of change:

It reveals that the variable "Goals" has the highest average score of 2.90, followed by Time to time (2.37) and Resistance (2.30). The average scores range from 2 to 3. It concludes that respondents agree on all of the factors mentioned.

Enhancement by change:

Table 2 displays the average score and rank for the variable "Discussion," which has the highest mean score of 2.44, followed by Individual performance (1.83). The average score ranges from 2 to 3. It concludes that respondents agree on all of the mentioned factors.

5. Results and Discussion:

Organizational changes implemented largely influence the department's goals. The majority of the youngsters among 23-25 years actively co-operate with the organization during change. Employees' involvement during a change may vary according to the employees' demographics. The majority of the organizations implement change to improve the level of the organization. Employees are discussed the change before being implemented in the organization although the employees might show some resistance to the change. Organizational change has less effect on an individual's performance in the organization.

6. Conclusion:

In today's increasingly diversified marketplaces, organisations must comprehend a wide range of demands and expectations in order to be strong clients and partners. Implementing organisational change helps the organisation function better. Businesses at risk of going out of business refuse to adapt. Change is challenging since it involves modifying people's attitudes and behaviours. Resistance often comes from workers who are skeptical of change initiatives. For organizational change to be successful, senior management should detail how the proposed change will help employees perform their duties more effectively and advance their careers. The survey found that employees have both positive and negative opinions about organizational change. In order to increase employee enthusiasm and help people overcome resistance and acquiescence to change, management should offer the proper change communication. By integrating staff members who can affect the transformation process or really contribute to future decisions, top management can enhance bottom-up communication.

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